

Correlation analysis of reactivity in the oxidation of substituted benzyl alcohols by quinolinium bromochromate

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Oxidation of benzyl alcohol and some *ortho*- *meta*- and *para*-monosubstituted ones by quinolinium, bromochromate (QBC) in dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) leads to the formation of corresponding benzaldehydes. The reaction is first order each in both QBC and the alcohol. The reaction is promoted by hydrogen ions; the hydrogen-ion dependence has the form $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b [\text{H}^+]$. Oxidation of α, α -dideuteriobenzyl alcohol (PhCD_2OH) has exhibited a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect ($k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}} = 5.60$ at 298 K). The reaction has been studied in nineteen organic solvents and the effect of solvent analysed using Taft's and Swain's multi-parametric equations. The rates of oxidation of *para*- and *meta*-substituted benzyl alcohols have been correlated in terms of Charton's triparametric LDR equation whereas the oxidation of *ortho*-substituted benzyl alcohols with tetraparametric LDRS equation. The oxidation of *para*-substituted benzyl alcohols is more susceptible to the delocalization effect than that of *ortho*- and *meta*-substituted compounds which display a greater dependence on the field effect. The positive value of η suggests the presence of an electron-deficient reaction centre in the rate-determining step. The reaction is subjected to steric acceleration by the *ortho*-substituents. A suitable mechanism has been proposed.

Quinolinium bromochromate (QBC), has been used as a mild and selective oxidant in synthetic organic chemistry¹. Only a few reports about the kinetic and mechanistic aspects of oxidation by QBC are available in the literature²⁻⁴. The kinetics of oxidation of benzyl alcohols by QBC has not been investigated. However, the oxidations of several primary aliphatic alcohols by QBC have already been reported⁵. We have been interested in kinetics of oxidations by Cr^{VI} species and have already published a few reports on oxidation by other pyridinium^{6,7} and quinolinium halochromates^{8,9}. In the present article we report the kinetics of oxidation of some monosubstituted benzyl alcohols by QBC in DMSO as solvent. Attempts have been made to correlate rate and structure in this reaction.

Results and discussion

The rates and other experimental data were obtained for all the alcohols. Since the results are similar, only representative data are reproduced here.

Stoichiometry : Oxidation of benzyl alcohols by QBC results in the oxidation of corresponding benzaldehydes. Analysis of products and the stoichiometric determinations indicate the following overall reaction (1).

QBC undergoes a two-electron change. This is in accord with the earlier observations with other halochromates^{10,11} as well as with QBC^{3,4}.

Rate laws : The reactions were found to be first order with respect to QBC. The individual kinetic runs were strictly first order to QBC. Further, the pseudo-first order rate constant, k_{obs} , was independent of initial concentration of QBC. The reaction rate increases linearly with an increase in the concentration of benzyl alcohols (Table 1).

Induced polymerisation of acrylonitrile : The oxidation of benzyl alcohol by QBC, in an atmosphere of nitrogen failed to induce the polymerisation of acrylonitrile. Further, an addition of a radical scavenger, acrylonitrile, had no effect on the rate (Table 1).

Effect of acidity : The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions. The hydrogen-ion dependence taking the form : $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b[\text{H}^+]$ (Table 1). The values for a and b for benzyl alcohol are $3.26 \pm 0.06 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $5.62 \pm 0.10 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively ($r^2 = 0.9988$).

Effect of substituents : The rates of oxidation of monosubstituted benzyl alcohols by QBC were determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated (Table 2).

Kinetic isotope effect : To ascertain the importance of

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of benzyl alcohol by QBC at 308 K

$10^3[\text{QBC}]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	[Alcohol] (mol dm ⁻³)	[TsOH] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)
1.0	0.10	0.0	3.30
1.0	0.20	0.0	6.46
1.0	0.40	0.0	13.1
1.0	0.60	0.0	19.5
1.0	0.80	0.0	25.7
1.0	1.00	0.0	32.4
2.0	0.40	0.0	14.2
4.0	0.40	0.0	12.7
6.0	0.40	0.0	13.5
8.0	0.40	0.0	14.0
1.0	1.00	0.1	38.1
1.0	1.00	0.2	44.3
1.0	1.00	0.4	55.2
1.0	1.00	0.6	65.1
1.0	1.00	0.8	78.3
1.0	1.00	1.0	88.8
1.0	0.40	0.0	13.3*

*Contained 0.001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

the cleavage of the α -C-H bond in the rate-determining step, oxidation of α,α -dideuteriobenzyl alcohol was studied. Results showed the presence of a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect (Table 2).

Effect of solvents : The oxidation of benzyl alcohol was studied in 19 different organic solvents. The choice of solvents was limited by the solubility of QBC and its reaction with primary and secondary alcohols. There was no reaction with the solvents chosen. Kinetics were similar in all the solvents. The values of k_2 are recorded in Table 3.

An isokinetic plot between $\log k_2$ at 288 K and at 318 K was linear ($r^2 = 0.9994$). The value of isokinetic temperature evaluated from the Exner's¹² plot is 635 ± 22 K. The linear isokinetic correlation implies that all the alcohols are oxidized by the same mechanism and the changes in the rate are governed by changes in both the enthalpy and entropy of activation.

An analysis of activation parameters has revealed that the entropy of activation ranges from -64 to -105 J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹. No definite trend could be observed in the variation of the entropy values in relation to the rate of the reac-

Table 2. Rate constants and activation parameters of the oxidation of substituted benzyl alcohols by QBC

Subst.	$10^4 k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				ΔH^* kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^* J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	ΔG^* kJ mol ⁻¹
	288	298	308	318 K			
H	5.67	13.5	32.4	76.5	63.5 ± 0.8	-87 ± 3	89.3 ± 0.7
<i>p</i> -Me	11.9	27.3	63.3	144	60.8 ± 0.8	-90 ± 3	88.7 ± 0.6
<i>p</i> -OMe	21.9	49.0	111	249	59.2 ± 0.8	-91 ± 3	86.1 ± 0.7
<i>p</i> -F	5.73	13.7	33.4	79.2	64.2 ± 0.9	-85 ± 3	89.3 ± 0.7
<i>p</i> -Cl	2.92	7.23	18.1	44.2	66.5 ± 0.9	-82 ± 3	90.9 ± 0.7
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	0.23	0.65	1.82	4.94	75.3 ± 0.8	-73 ± 2	96.8 ± 0.8
<i>p</i> -CF ₃	0.71	1.88	5.00	13.0	71.3 ± 0.9	-77 ± 3	94.2 ± 0.6
<i>p</i> -COOMe	1.00	2.61	6.81	17.3	69.9 ± 0.8	-79 ± 3	93.4 ± 0.6
<i>p</i> -Br	2.88	7.09	17.8	43.3	66.5 ± 0.9	-82 ± 3	91.0 ± 0.8
<i>p</i> -NHAc	11.0	25.4	60.3	135	61.6 ± 0.8	-88 ± 3	87.7 ± 0.6
<i>p</i> -CN	0.41	1.12	3.07	8.61	73.4 ± 0.8	-74 ± 3	95.5 ± 0.7
<i>p</i> -SMe	13.3	30.5	71.3	162	60.8 ± 0.8	-89 ± 2	87.3 ± 0.4
<i>p</i> -NMe ₂	108	222	470	696	53.3 ± 0.8	-98 ± 3	82.4 ± 0.5
<i>m</i> -Me	9.65	22.5	53.4	126	62.7 ± 0.9	-86 ± 3	88.0 ± 0.4
<i>m</i> -OMe	9.42	22.0	51.6	119	61.9 ± 0.8	-89 ± 3	88.1 ± 0.6
<i>m</i> -Cl	1.82	4.75	12.6	31.1'	69.7 ± 0.6	-75 ± 2	91.9 ± 0.7
<i>m</i> -Br	1.78	4.60	12.2	29.7	69.2 ± 0.7	-77 ± 2	92.0 ± 0.6
<i>m</i> -F	2.18	5.61	15.0	36.6	69.4 ± 0.7	-75 ± 2	91.5 ± 0.5
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	0.23	0.66	1.96	5.41	77.8 ± 0.9	-64 ± 3	96.8 ± 0.7
<i>m</i> -CO ₂ Me	1.08	2.81	7.50	18.3	69.6 ± 0.7	-80 ± 2	93.2 ± 0.5

Table-2 (contd.)

<i>m</i> -CF ₃	0.74	2.04	5.53	14.3	72.7 ± 0.6	-72 ± 2	94.0 ± 0.6
<i>m</i> -CN	0.41	1.13	3.21	8.55	74.8 ± 0.9	-70 ± 3	95.4 ± 0.6
<i>m</i> -SMe	6.63	15.9	38.3	88.8	63.4 ± 0.6	-86 ± 2	88.9 ± 0.7
<i>m</i> -NHAc	6.06	14.0	35.1	77.4	62.6 ± 0.9	-90 ± 3	89.1 ± 0.7
<i>o</i> -Me	45.8	98.1	201	421	53.8 ± 0.6	-103 ± 2	84.5 ± 0.7
<i>o</i> -OMe	40.3	87.3	181	390	55.2 ± 0.7	-100 ± 2	84.7 ± 0.5
<i>o</i> -NO ₂	0.54	1.49	4.03	10.7	73.2 ± 0.7	-73 ± 2	94.8 ± 0.8
<i>o</i> -COOMe	3.85	9.51	22.5	54.0	64.6 ± 0.6	-87 ± 2	90.2 ± 0.6
<i>o</i> -NHAc	58.2	124	250	518	52.6 ± 0.6	-105 ± 2	84.0 ± 0.8
<i>o</i> -Cl	10.3	24.6	55.4	121	60.4 ± 0.1	-93 ± 1	87.9 ± 0.7
<i>o</i> -Br	13.4	31.0	69.3	147	56.6 ± 0.3	-99 ± 1	86.1 ± 0.8
<i>o</i> -I	22.1	49.5	108	227	71.7 ± 0.4	-73 ± 1	93.1 ± 0.9
<i>o</i> -CN	1.12	2.97	7.68	19.1	52.6 ± 0.6	-105 ± 2	83.9 ± 0.7
<i>o</i> -SMe	55.4	119	241	501	53.3 ± 0.5	-104 ± 2	84.0 ± 0.8
<i>o</i> -F	6.42	15.3	37.2	86.4	63.6 ± 0.7	-86 ± 2	89.0 ± 0.7
<i>o</i> -CF ₃	8.20	19.1	43.3	99.2	60.6 ± 0.8	-94 ± 2	88.5 ± 0.8
α,α'-BA	0.98	2.41	5.97	14.4	66.0 ± 0.9	-93 ± 3	93.6 ± 0.7
<i>k</i> _H / <i>k</i> _D	5.79	5.60	5.43	5.31			

Table 3. Solvent effect on the oxidation of benzyl alcohol by QBC at 308 K

Solvent	10 ⁴ <i>k</i> ₂ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	Solvent	10 ⁴ <i>k</i> ₂ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
Chloroform	9.12	Toluene	3.16
1,2-Dichloroethane	11.7	Acetophenone	15.5
Dichloromethane	10.9	Tetrahydrofuran	5.37
Dimethyl sulfoxide	32.4	<i>t</i> -Butyl alcohol	4.47
Acetone	10.2	1,4-Dioxane	6.03
DMF	17.8	1,2-Dimethoxyethane	2.95
Butanone	7.94	Ethyl acetate	3.89
Nitrobenzene	14.8	Carbon disulfide	1.62
Benzene	3.63	Acetic acid	2.45
Cyclohexane	0.39		

tion. The alcohols reacting at a faster rate tend to exhibit lower enthalpy of activation, whereas the less reactive alcohols exhibit higher enthalpies of activation. This is an expected trend.

The observed hydrogen-ion dependence suggests that the reaction follows two mechanistic pathways, one acid-independent and another acid-dependent. The acid-catalysis may well be attributed to a protonation of QBC as (eq. 2) to yield a protonated Cr^{VI} species which is a stronger oxidant and electrophile. Formation of a protonated Cr^{VI} species has earlier been postulated in the reactions of structurally similar PFC¹³.

The rate constants, *k*₂, in seventeen solvents (CS₂ was not considered as the complete range of solvent parameters was not available) did not yield significant correlation in terms of linear solvation energy relationship (3) of Kamlet *et al.*¹⁴.

$$\log k_2 = A_0 + p\pi^* + b\beta + a\alpha \quad (3)$$

The data on the solvent effect were also analysed in terms of Swain's equation¹⁵ of cation- and anion-solvating concept of the solvents, eq. (4).

$$\log k_2 = aA + bB + C \quad (4)$$

Here *A* represents the anion-solvating power of the solvent and *B* the cation-solvating power of the solvent. *C* is the intercept term. (*A* + *B*) is postulated to represent the solvent polarity. The rates in different solvents were analysed in terms of eq. (4), separately with *A* and *B* and with (*A* + *B*).

$$\log k_2 = 0.72 (\pm 0.03) A + 1.66 (\pm 0.02) B - 3.49 \quad (5)$$

$$R^2 = 0.9970; \text{sd} = 0.03; n = 19; \psi = 0.06$$

$$\log k_2 = 0.48 (\pm 0.55) A - 2.47 \quad (6)$$

$$r^2 = 0.0431; \text{sd} = 0.44; n = 19; \psi = 1.00$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.61 (\pm 0.15) B - 3.73 \quad (7)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9020; \text{sd} = 0.74; n = 19; \psi = 0.32$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.55 \pm 0.12 (A + B) - 3.52 \quad (8)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8836; sd = 0.15; n = 19; \psi = 0.25$$

Here n is the number of data points and ψ is Exner's statistical parameter¹⁶.

The rates of oxidation of benzyl alcohol in different solvents show an excellent correlation in Swain's eq. (5) with the cation-solvating power playing the major role. In fact, the cation-solvation alone accounts for *ca.* 99% of the data. The solvent polarity, represented by $(A + B)$, also accounted for *ca.* 88% of the data. In view of the fact that the solvent polarity is able to account for *ca.* 88% of the data, an attempt was made to correlate the rate with the relative permittivity of the solvent. However, a plot of $\log(\text{rate})$ against the inverse of the relative permittivity is not linear ($r^2 = 0.5519$, $sd = 0.31$, $\psi = 0.70$).

Correlation analysis of reactivity: In this work we have applied the Charton's¹⁷ LDR eq. (9) to the rate constants, k_2 .

$$\log k_2 = L \sigma_1 + D \sigma_d + R \sigma_e + h \quad (9)$$

Here, σ_1 is a localized (field and/or inductive) effect parameter, σ_d is the intrinsic delocalized electrical effect parameter when active site electronic demand is minimal and σ_e represents the sensitivity of the substituent to changes in electronic demand by the active site. The latter two substituent parameters are related by eq. (10).

$$\sigma_D = \eta \sigma_e + \sigma_d \quad (10)$$

Here η represents the electronic demand of the reaction site and is given by $\eta = R/D$, and σ_D represents the delocalized electrical parameter of the diparametric LD equation.

For *ortho*-substituted compounds, it is necessary to account for the possibility of steric effects and Charton¹⁷, therefore, modified the LDR equation to generate the LDRS eq. (11).

$$\log k_2 = L \sigma_1 + D \sigma_d + R \sigma_e + S \upsilon + h \quad (11)$$

where υ is the well known Charton's steric parameter based on Van der Waals radii¹⁸.

The rates of oxidation of *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-substituted benzyl alcohols show an excellent correlation in terms of the LDR/LDRS equations (Table 4).

The comparison of the L and D values for the substituted benzyl alcohols showed that the oxidation of *para*-substituted benzyl alcohols is more susceptible to the delocalization effect than to the localized effect. However, the oxidation of *ortho*- and *meta*-substituted compounds exhibited a greater dependence on the field effect. In all the cases, the magnitude of the reaction constants decreases with an increase in the temperature, pointing to a decrease in selectivity with an increase in temperature.

All three regression coefficients, L , D and R , are negative indicating an electron-deficient carbon centre in the activated complex for the rate-determining step. The positive value of η adds a negative increment to σ_d , reflecting the electron-donating power of the substituent and its

Table 4. Temperature dependence for the reaction constants for the oxidation of substituted benzyl alcohols by QBC

T/K	L	D	R	S	η	R^2	sd	ψ	P_D	P_s
<i>para</i> -substituted										
288	-1.76	-1.92	-1.20	-	0.63	0.9990	0.028	0.04	53.0	-
298	-1.61	-1.82	-1.14	-	0.62	0.9989	0.026	0.03	53.1	-
308	-1.52	-1.73	-1.09	-	0.63	0.9990	0.025	0.04	53.2	-
318	-1.44	-1.65	-1.02	-	0.62	0.9990	0.023	0.04	53.4	-
<i>meta</i> -substituted										
288	-1.84	-1.29	-0.98	-	0.70	0.9999	0.005	0.01	41.2	-
298	-1.70	-1.25	-0.90	-	0.72	0.9992	0.017	0.03	42.4	-
308	-1.57	-1.20	-0.83	-	0.69	0.9993	0.015	0.03	43.3	-
318	-1.47	-1.17	-0.75	-	0.64	0.9973	0.028	0.06	44.3	-
<i>ortho</i> -substituted										
288	-1.85	-1.38	-0.46	1.27	0.33	0.9913	0.190	0.29	42.7	28.2
298	-1.74	-1.31	-0.46	1.21	0.35	0.9927	0.180	0.28	43.0	28.4
308	-1.62	-1.23	-0.35	1.12	0.28	0.9939	0.160	0.28	43.2	28.2
318	-1.53	-1.17	-0.47	1.02	0.30	0.9926	0.160	0.29	43.5	27.4

capacity to stabilise a cationic species. The positive value of S indicates that the reaction is subject to steric acceleration by an *ortho*-substituent.

The percent contribution¹⁸ of the delocalized effect, P_D , is given by eq. (12).

$$P_D = (|D| \times 100)/(|L| + |D|) \quad (12)$$

Similarly, the percent contribution of the steric parameter¹⁸ to the total effect of the substituent, P_s , was determined by using eq. (13).

$$P_s = (|S| \times 100)/(|L| + |D| + |S|) \quad (13)$$

The values of P_D and P_s are also recorded in Table 4. The value of P_D for the oxidation of *para*-substituted benzyl alcohols is *ca.* 53% whereas the corresponding values for the *meta*- and *ortho*-substituted alcohols are *ca.* 42 and 43% respectively. This shows that the balance of localization and delocalization effects is different for differently substituted benzyl alcohols. The less pronounced resonance effect from the *ortho*-position than from the *para*-position may be due to the twisting away of the alcoholic group from the plane of the benzene ring. The magnitude of the P_s value shows that the steric effect is significant in this reaction.

The positive value of S showed a steric acceleration of the reaction. This may be explained on the basis of high ground state energy of the sterically crowded alcohols. Since the crowding is relieved in the product aldehyde as well as the transition state leading to it, the transition state energy of the crowded and uncrowded alcohols do not differ much and steric acceleration, therefore results.

The high reactivity of *p*-NMe₂ substituted compound is due to the high electron donating capacity of the group. Further, this being a large substituent, its steric interaction is large. This also contributes to the rate-enhancing effect of the substituent.

Mechanism :

A hydrogen abstraction mechanism leading to the formation of the free radicals is unlikely in view of the failure to induce polymerization of acrylonitrile and no effect of the radical scavenger on the reaction rate. The presence of a substantial kinetic isotope effect confirms the cleavage of a α -C-H bond in the rate-determining step. The negative values of the localization and delocalization electrical effects i.e. of L , D and R points to an electron-deficient reaction centre in the rate-determining step. It is further supported by the positive value of η , which indi-

cates that the substituent is better able to stabilise a cationic or electron-deficient reactive site. Therefore, a hydride-ion transfer in the rate-determining step is suggested. The hydride-ion transfer mechanism is also supported by the major role of cation-solvating power of the solvents. The hydride ion transfer may take place either by a cyclic process via an ester intermediate or by an acyclic one-step bimolecular process. Kwart and Nickle¹⁹ have shown that a dependence of kinetic isotope effect on temperature can be gainfully employed to determine whether the loss of hydrogen proceeds through a concerted cyclic process or by an acyclic one. The data for protio- and deuterio-benzyl alcohols, fitted to the familiar expression : $k_H/k_D = A_H/A_D (-\Delta H^*/RT)^{20,21}$ show a direct correspondence with the properties of a symmetrical transition state in which activation energy difference for protio and deuterio compounds is equal to the difference in the zero-point energy for the respective C-H and C-D bonds (≈ 4.5 kJ mol⁻¹) and the entropies of activation of the respective reactions are almost equal. Similar phenomena were observed earlier in the oxidation of aliphatic alcohols by QFC⁹ and QBC⁵. Bordwell²² has documented a very cogent evidence against the occurrence of concerted one-step bimolecular process by hydrogen transfer and it is evident that in the present studies also the hydrogen transfer does not occur by an acyclic biomolecular process. It is well-established that intrinsically concerted sigmatropic reactions, characterised by transfer of hydrogen in a cyclic transition state, are the only truly symmetrical process involving a linear hydrogen transfer²³. Littler²⁴ has also shown that a cyclic hydride transfer, in the oxidation of alcohols by Cr^{VI}, involves six electrons and, being a Huckel-type system, is an allowed process. Thus, a transition state having a planar, cyclic and symmetrical structure can be envisaged for the decomposition of the ester intermediate. Hence, the overall mechanism is proposed to involve the formation of a chromate ester in a fast pre-equilibrium step and then a decomposition of the ester in a subsequent slow step via a cyclic concerted symmetrical transition state leading to the product (Schemes 1 and 2).

The observed negative value of entropy of activation also supports the proposed mechanism. As the charge separation takes place in the transition state, the charged ends become highly solvated. This results in an immobilization of a large number of solvent molecules, reflected in the loss of entropy²⁵.

Materials and methods :

QBC was prepared by the reported method¹ and its

Acid-dependent path :

Scheme 1

Acid-dependent path :

Scheme 2

purity checked by an iodometric method. The procedure used for the purification of alcohols has been described earlier²⁶. α,α -Dideuteriobenzyl alcohol (PhCH_2OH) was prepared by the reported method²⁷. Its isotopic purity, as ascertained by its NMR spectra, was $95 \pm 4\%$. Due to non-aqueous nature of the solvent, toluene-*p*-sulphonic acid (TsOH) was used as a source of hydrogen ions. Solvents were purified by the usual methods²⁸.

Product analysis : The product analysis was carried out under kinetic conditions. In a typical experiment, benzyl alcohol (5.4 g, 0.05 mol) and QBC (3.10 g, 0.01 mol) were made up to 50 cm³ in DMSO and kept in the dark for *ca.* 15 h to ensure completion of the reaction. The solution was then treated with an excess (200 cm³) of a saturated solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in 2 mol dm⁻³ HCl and kept overnight in a refrigerator. The precipitated 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (DNP) was filtered off, dried, weighed, recrystallized from ethanol, and weighed again. The yields of DNP before and after recrystallization were 2.62 g (92%) and 2.23 g (78%) respectively. The DNP was found identical (m.p. and mixed

m.p.) with the DNP of benzaldehyde. Similar experiments were performed with other alcohols also. The oxidation state of chromium in completely reduced reaction mixtures, determined by an iodometric method was 3.94 ± 0.10 .

Kinetic measurements : The pseudo-first order conditions were attained by maintaining a large excess ($\times 15$ or more) of the alcohol over QBC. The solvent was DMSO, unless specified otherwise. The reactions were followed, at constant temperatures (± 0.1 K), by monitoring the decrease in [QBC] spectrophotometrically at 365 nm. No other reactant or product has any significant absorption at this wavelength. The pseudo-first order rate constant, k_{obs} , was evaluated from the linear ($r = 0.990 - 0.999$) plots of $\log [\text{QBC}]$ against time for up to 80% reaction. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$. The second order rate constant, k_2 , was obtained from the relation: $k_2 = k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{alcohol}]$. All experiments, other than those for studying the effect of hydrogen ions, were carried out in the absence of TsOH.

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